

D3.2. Proceedings from the Summer school on directed evolution of proteins

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (CasProt)**
No. 952333

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Summer School on Directed Evolution of Proteins was held for the first time at the Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences TIP-UPJŠ in Košice from May 2nd to May 12th, 2023. The school provided participants with a comprehensive understanding of protein evolution and expression and purification. The program integrated practical laboratory sessions with lectures delivered by experts in the field.

The primary focus of the Summer School was to introduce participants to the efficient protein evolution method known as a ribosome display. The students had the opportunity to learn the fundamentals of this technique by actively engaging in all the necessary experimental steps. The Summer School also included lectures delivered by researchers from Pavol Jozef Šafárik University, Universität Zürich, and the Slovak Academy of Sciences. These lectures covered a wide range of topics related to protein evolution, including protein engineering strategies and the principles of directed evolution.

Eight students actively participated in the Summer School. The program spanned two weeks, with each week focusing on different aspects of protein evolution and engineering. During the first week, students were introduced to various methods including error-prone PCR, restriction digestion, ligation, or cell transformation. Notable lectures were given by Andreas Plückthun, world-recognized scientist and professor in the field of protein engineering and directed evolution, who along with his research team, has made significant contributions to the development and optimization of the ribosome display technique. The first week concluded with laboratory work sessions. All laboratory sessions were led by researchers working at CIB TIP UPJŠ, namely Ľuboš Ambro and Mária Tomková.

The second week of the Summer School focused on specific laboratory work related to plasmid isolation, preparation for ribosome display, and the actual practice of ribosome display. Participants were engaged in intensive laboratory sessions, allowing them to apply their theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the context of directed protein evolution.

The Summer School ended up with presentations and closing remarks on Friday, May 12th. Participants had the opportunity to showcase their work and share their findings from the practical sessions conducted throughout the program. The presentations provided a platform for students to demonstrate their understanding of the ribosome display technique and its applications in directed protein evolution.

Overall, the Summer School on Directed Evolution of Proteins offered a comprehensive learning experience to the participants, combining lectures by experts with hands-on laboratory sessions. The integration of theory and practice provided students with the necessary skills and knowledge to pursue further research in the field of protein engineering.

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1. Summer school program

2nd – 12th May 2023, Košice

1st Week

Tuesday 2.5.2023

9:00 Erik Sedlák Welcome and opening remarks
9:05-9:50 Andreas Plückhahn Protein evolution
10:05-10:50 Daniel Rozbesky Mammalian cell based protein production
11:05-11:50 Lenka Džurová Molecular Farming in Barley
12:00-13:00 Lunch
13:00-13:30 Mária Tomková Evolution of thrombolytic drug staphylokinase by ribosome display
13:30-17:00 Work in the laboratory

Wednesday 3.5.2023

9:00-9:45 Martin Toul Rational protein engineering driven by kinetics
10:00-10:45 Michal Nemergut Identifying a new aggregation hotspot in Alzheimer's disease : Opportunities for drug discovery
11:00-11:45 Ľuboš Ambro Production and purification of recombinant proteins: pitfalls and problem solving
12:00-13:00 Lunch
13:00-17:00 Work in the laboratory

Thursday 4.5.2023

9:00-9:45 Stanislav Stuchlík Solubility as a challenge for expression and purification of recombinant proteins
10:05-10:50 Rostislav Škrabana Preparation of intrinsically disordered proteins
11:05-11:50 Veronika Hovanová From macroscopic measurements to microscopic events
12:00-13:00 Lunch
13:00-17:00 Work in the laboratory

Friday 4.5.2023

9:00-9:45 Gabriel Žoldák The application of nanomechanical studies for protein engineering
10:00-10:45 Veronika Huntošová Fluorescence and imaging of proteins in cells
11:00-11:45 Erik Sedlák Genetically encoded photosensitizers
12:00 Erik Sedlák Closing remarks
12:00-13:00 Lunch
13:00-16:00 Work in the laboratory

2nd Week

Tuesday 9.5.2023

8:00-12:00 Plasmid isolation, Preparation for ribosome display
12:00-13:00 Lunch
13:00-17:00 Work in the laboratory

Wednesday 10.5.2023

8:00-12:00 Ribosome display – illustration
12:00-13:00 Lunch
13:00-17:00 Work in the laboratory

Thursday 11.5.2023

8:00-12:00 Ribosome display - practice (workshop participants)
12:00-13:00 Lunch
13:00-17:00 Work in the laboratory

Friday 12.5.2023

9:00-12:00 Presentations, closing remarks
12:00-13:00 Lunch

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant

2. Program details and selected abstracts of lectures

Protein evolution

Andreas Plückthun

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Ribosome display is an in vitro evolution technology for proteins. It is based on in vitro translation but prevents the newly synthesized protein and the mRNA encoding it from leaving the ribosome. It thereby couples phenotype and genotype. Since no cells need to be transformed, very large libraries can be used directly in selections, and the in vitro amplification provides a very convenient integration of random mutagenesis that can be incorporated into the procedure. This review highlights concepts, mechanisms, and different variations of ribosome display and compares it to related methods. Applications of ribosome display are summarized, e.g., the directed evolution of proteins for higher binding affinity, higher stability or other improved biophysical parameters and enzymatic properties. Ribosome display has developed into a robust technology used in academia and industry alike, and it has made the cell-free Darwinian evolution of proteins over multiple generations a reality.

Evolution of thrombolytic drug staphylokinase by ribosome display

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Directed evolution represents a powerful strategy for the development of therapeutic proteins with improved properties [1]. By harnessing the principles of evolution, researchers can rapidly generate protein variants that exhibit enhanced affinity, stability, or specificity, enabling the creation of more effective and tailored therapeutics. The process of directed evolution involves iterative cycles of mutagenesis, selection, and amplification. There are several techniques of directed evolution that can be generally divided into cellular approaches, including phage and yeast display, and cell-free approaches represented by ribosome or mRNA display.

We employed ribosome display to improve a thrombolytic agent, staphylokinase (SAK). The usage of currently available thrombolytics is limited due to their high immunogenicity and haemorrhagic complications. SAK is a single-chain extracellular protein secreted by *Staphylococcus aureus*. It initiates the fibrinolytic cascade to help invading bacteria move deeper into the tissues. Owing to its thrombolytic properties and high fibrin specificity, it is considered a promising new thrombolytic agent. However, not all

SAK features are optimized for its practical applications, leaving room for improvement. Engineering the affinity and selectivity of SAK could increase its residence time on plasmin, thus reducing the severity of side effects.

Directed evolution has been used to optimize the activity, stability and solubility of therapeutic proteins. Continued advancements in directed evolution techniques and technologies hold great promise for the future of protein engineering and the development of novel therapeutic interventions.

Production and purification of recombinant proteins

Ľ. Ambro

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Recombinant protein expression frequently necessitates rigorous planning and process optimization to determine the ideal host, culture condition, as well as the best feasible purification technique to ensure a high yield with the fewest possible quality lost. Both protein expression and purification are frequently difficult and complex processes because of the overall complexity that proteins have by nature. There is no "one size fits all" method, and the expression and purification of each protein needs to be tailored to the specific situation. The lecture will discuss most often problems encountered during the process of protein production in *E. coli* with particular focus on cloning, expression, and purification steps.

3. Summer school trainings and experiments

GENERAL METHODS

Error-prone PCR

1. Amplify SAK gene by using two different concentrations (3 μ M and 10 μ M) of nucleotide analogues **8-oxo-dGTP and dPTP** (JenaBioScience) and **Taq polymerase** (NEB).

	Final. c.	3 μ M		10 μ M		0 μ M (CTRL)
		1x (50 ul)	3x (50 ul)	1x (50 ul)	3x (50 ul)	1x (50 ul)
10x Thermopol buffer	1x	5	15	5	15	5
dNTPs (10 mM)	400 μ M	2	6	2	6	2
8-oxo-dGTP (100 μM)	3-5-10 μ M	1,5	4,5	5	15	0
dPTP (100 μM)	3-5-10 M	1,5	4,5	5	15	0
SAK_FW (100 μM)	500 nM	0,25	0,75	0,25	0,75	0,25
SAK_REV (100 μM)	500 nM	0,25	0,75	0,25	0,75	0,25
Taq polymerase (1 U/ul)	2.5 U/5 0ul	2,5	7,5	2,5	7,5	2,5
DNA (30 ng/ul)		1	3	1	3	1
H₂O		36	108	29	87	39
Total		50	150	50	150	50

PCR	Number of cycles	Min	°C
Touchdown	1x	5	95°C
	10x	0:30	95°C
		0:40	70°-61°C
		0:50	72°C
	20x	0:30	95°C
		0:40	60°C
		0:50	72°C
	1x	5:00	72°C
	forever		10°C

2. Analyse PCR product on 1.5% agarose gel and extract from the gel via Qiagen kit.

Figure 1. Agarose gel with SAK DNA library.

3. Extract DNA from gel using QIAquick gel extraction kit. Ligate extracted PCR fragment into digested pQE vector by T4 ligase using molar ratio 1:10 (plasmid:insert). After one hour, transform ligation mix (5 μ l) to 50 μ l competent *E. coli* XL1Blue cells via heat shock method. Streak transform cells onto the agar plates with ampicillin and incubated overnight at 37 °C.
4. Pick a 6-8 single colonies for each concentration of nucleotide analogues from a freshly streaked selective plate and inoculate a culture of 5 ml 2YT medium containing the appropriate selective antibiotic (ampicillin). Incubate for 12–16 h at 37°C with vigorous shaking (250rpm). Growth for more than 16 h is not recommended because cells begin to lyse, and plasmid DNA yields may be reduced. Use a tube or flask with a volume of at least 4 times the volume of the culture.
5. Isolate plasmid via QIAprep.

Preparation of agarose gel

1. Prepare 1X TAE buffer by adding 20 mL of 50X TAE Buffer to 980 mL water.
2. Chose % agarose for gel. A 1% or 1.5% agarose gel will work for most applications.

Range of separation	% agarose	Amount of agarose for 90 mL gel
500 bp – 7 kb	1	0.9 g
400 bp – 6 kb	1.2	1.1 g
200 bp – 3 kb	1.5	1.35 g

3. Add desired amount of agarose to 1X TAE buffer in a flask. For a standard gel, use 90 mL of 1X TAE Buffer. Swirl the flask to mix.
4. Microwave solution for 2 min. Remove with gloves and swirl. Microwave for longer if there is undissolved agarose. Allow the solution to cool for couple minutes.
5. Add 5 μ l of ethidium bromide to tray and mix carefully with comb.
 - Note: Ethidium bromide is a carcinogen and must be handled with care. Use nitrile gloves. Dispose ethidium bromide tips in the designated biohazard bin.
6. Place the gel tray into the cassette and pour the solution into the tray. Insert the comb into the top of the gel and allow the gel to solidify for 1 hour. Avoid bubbles in the gel.
 - Choose either 10- or 16-well gel depending on application. If performing gel extractions, use the 10- well comb to accommodate a larger mass of DNA.
7. Rinse with water and dry the flask to prevent residual gel from solidifying in the flask.

Running gel electrophoresis

1. Once the gel has solidified, carefully remove the comb by pulling straight up.

2. Ensure the gel is in the correct orientation, with the negative/black electrode above the wells so that the DNA runs toward the positive/red electrode.
3. Prepare the samples by adding 5X loading buffer to each. For a 10-well gel, combine 20 μL of DNA with 5 μL of 5X loading buffer in order to load 25 μL . [For most applications, load 20-100 ng of DNA/lane.] If doing a gel extraction in a 10-well gel, combine 20 μL DNA with 5 μL 5X loading buffer to load 25 μL .
 - Note: These samples can be prepared on the reverse side of paraffin paper since the volume is so small.
4. Load 8 μL of DNA ladder into one lane of your gel.
 - Note: Choose a ladder that contains the weights of your sample.
5. Load samples into wells. Avoid bubbles.
6. Place lid on cassette and ensure the red and black wires are connected to the matching red and black electrodes on the cassette.
7. Gel can be run at a variety of time and voltage settings depending on the size of samples and desired separation. For most samples, 100V for 15-60 min will work.
8. Remove the tray with the gel and image with UV. Exercise caution when imaging with UV, especially if doing a gel extraction over the UV box.
9. If doing gel extraction, proceed with gel. If not, dispose of the gel in the gel biohazard bin.

Digestion

1. Prepare a reaction mix by adding reagents in the order indicated in table below.
2. Incubate at 37°C for 1 hours, no shaking.

Reagent	Volume (μL)
Cut Smart Buffer (10X)	5 μL
DNA	1-5 μg
Restriction enzyme 1 (20 U/μg DNA)	1-5 μL
Restriction enzyme 2 (20 U/μg DNA)	1-5 μL
Nuclease-Free Water	As required to make up final reaction volume
Final reaction volume	50 μL

Final DNA concentration: 20-100 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$.

Restriction enzyme 1: 20 U/ μL .

Restriction enzyme 2: 20 U/ μL .

Ligation

1. Prepare the following reaction mixture:

Linear vector DNA	100 ng
Insert DNA	10:1 molar ratio over vector
10 x T4 DNA Ligase buffer	2 μ L
Thermo Scientific T4 DNA Ligase	1 U
Water, nuclease-free	to 20 μ L
Total volume	20 μL

2. Incubate 1 hour at 21 °C.
3. Use 5 μ L of the mixture for transformation of 50 μ L of chemically competent cells or use 1-2 μ L per 50 μ L electrocompetent cells.
4. Heat inactivation of T4 DNA Ligase at at 70 °C for 5 minutes for electroporation.

PCR purification (Qiagen QIAquick PCR purification kit)

1. Add 5 volumes of Buffer PB to 1 volume of the PCR sample and mix (For example, add 500 μ l of Buffer PB to 100 μ l PCR sample).
2. Place a QIAquick spin column in a provided 2 ml collection tube.
3. To bind DNA, apply the sample to the QIAquick column and centrifuge for 60 s.
4. Discard flow-through. Place the QIAquick column back into the same tube. Collection tubes are re-used to reduce plastic waste.
5. To wash, add 0.70 ml Buffer PE to the QIAquick column and centrifuge for 60 s.
6. Discard flow-through and place the QIAquick column back in the same tube. Centrifuge the column for an additional 2 min.
7. Place QIAquick column in a clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube.
8. To elute DNA, add 35 μ l or water (pH 7.0–8.5) to the center of the QIAquick membrane. For increased DNA concentration, let the column stand for 1 min, and then centrifuge and centrifuge the column for 1 min.

Gel extraction (Qiagen QIAquick gel extraction kit)

1. Excise the DNA fragment from the agarose gel with a clean, sharp scalpel.
2. Weigh the gel slice in a colorless tube. Add 3 volumes Buffer QG to 1 volume gel (100 mg gel ~ 100 μ l). The maximum amount of gel per spin column is 400 mg.
3. Incubate at 50°C for 10 min. Vortex the tube every 2–3 min to help dissolve gel.

4. Add 1 gel volume isopropanol to the sample and mix.
5. Place a QIAquick spin column in a provided 2 ml collection tube or into a vacuum manifold. To bind DNA, apply the sample to the QIAquick column and centrifuge for 1 min or apply vacuum to the manifold until all the samples have passed through the column. Discard flow-through and place the QIAquick column back into the same tube. For sample volumes > 800 µl, load and spin/apply vacuum again.
6. Add 500 µl Buffer QG to the QIAquick column and centrifuge for 1 min or apply vacuum. Discard flow-through and place the QIAquick column back into the same tube.
7. To wash, add 700 µl Buffer PE to QIAquick column and centrifuge for 1 min or apply vacuum. Discard flow-through and place the QIAquick column back into the same tube. Let the column stand 2–5 min after addition of Buffer PE. Centrifuge the QIAquick column in the provided 2 ml collection tube for 1 min to remove residual wash buffer.
8. Place QIAquick column into a clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube.
9. To elute DNA, add 35 µl water to the center of the QIAquick membrane and centrifuge the column for 1 min. For increased DNA concentration, let the column stand for up to 4 min, and then centrifuge for 1 min.

Plasmid isolation (QIAprep mini)

1. Harvest the bacterial cells by centrifugation at > 8000 rpm (6800 x g) in a conventional table-top microcentrifuge for 3 min at room temperature.
2. Resuspend pelleted bacterial cells in 250 µl Buffer P1 and transfer to a microcentrifuge tube. No cell clumps should be visible after resuspension of the pellet. The bacteria should be resuspended completely by vortexing or pipetting up and down until no cell clumps remain.
3. Add 250 µl Buffer P2 and mix thoroughly by inverting the tube 4–6 times. Mix gently by inverting the tube. Do not vortex, because this will result in shearing of genomic DNA and contamination of plasmid. If continue inverting the tube until the solution becomes viscous and slightly clear. Do not allow the lysis reaction to proceed for more than 5 min.
4. Add 350 µl Buffer N3. Mix immediately and thoroughly by inverting the tube 4–6 times.
To avoid localized precipitation, mix the solution thoroughly, immediately after addition of Buffer N3. Large culture volumes (e.g., ≥ 5 ml) may require inverting up to 10 times. The solution should become cloudy.
5. Centrifuge for 10 min at 13,000 rpm (~ 17,900 x g) in a table-top microcentrifuge. A compact white pellet will form.
6. Apply 750 µl of the supernatant from step 4 to the QIAprep 2.0 Spin Column by pipetting.
7. Centrifuge for 60 s. Discard the flow through.

8. Wash the QIAprep 2.0 Spin Column by adding 0.5 ml Buffer PB and centrifuging for 60 s. Discard the flow through.
9. Wash QIAprep 2.0 Spin Column by adding 0.70 ml Buffer PE and centrifuging for 60 s.
10. Repeat step 9.
11. Discard the flow through, and centrifuge at full speed for an additional 2 min to remove residual wash buffer.
12. Place the QIAprep 2.0 Spin Column in a clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube. To elute DNA, add 50 μ l Buffer EB (10 mM Tris·Cl, pH 8.5) or water to the center of each QIAprep 2.0 Spin Column, let stand for 1 min, and centrifuge for 1 min.

Bacterial chemical transformation

1. Transfer the required number of tubes from -70° C freezer to wet ice. Include an extra tube for control DNA, if desired.
2. Allow the cells to thaw for 10-20 minutes. Gently tap the tubes multiple times to obtain uniform suspension
 - a. For control: Add 1 μ L (10 ng) pUC19 control DNA to one tube. Mix by gentle tapping and place on ice.
 - b. Add 1 ng to 50 ng of purified plasmid DNA or 5 μ l of ligation mixture directly to cells in rest of the tubes (50 μ l). Mix by gentle tapping and place on ice.
3. Incubate the cells on ice for 30 minutes.
4. Transfer the cells to 42° C thermo-block for exactly 45 seconds.
5. Transfer the cells to ice for 2 minutes.
6. Add prewarmed SOC or 2YT medium to each tube. Transfer the cells to sterile polypropylene tubes and loosen the caps to facilitate aeration of the cultures.
7. Incubates the cells on shaker incubator (225-250 rpm) at 37° C for 1 hour.
8. Pipette 10-100 μ L of each transformed cell suspension onto LB or 2YT agar plates with selection antibiotic and spread it using sterile spreader.
9. Incubate plates at 37° C overnight.

RIBOSOME DISPLAY FOR SELECTION FOR STAPHYLOKINASE SELECTION

Equipment and reagents

General

- Adhesive plate sealers (Thermo Scientific, No. AB-0580);
- Sterile, RNase-free filter tips (Molecular Bio Products) – 10, 100 and 1000 µl;
- Sterile, RNase-free SafeLock 1.5 and 2.0 ml tubes;
- Sterile 0.2 PCR tubes;
- Sterile 15 ml and 50 ml Falcon tubes;
- 0.22 µm filter (for syringes) and 50 ml and 2 ml syringes;
- RNase, DNase free water;
- Outer pRDV primers:
T7B (forward, outer primer): introduces T7 promoter and part of the stabilizing 5' loop;
tolAkurz (reverse, outer primer): binds in the tolA spacer region and introduces a stabilizing 3' loop.

Kits:

- QIAquick Gel Extraction kit (250);
- QIAquick PCR purification kit (250);
- Illustra ProbeQuant G-50 Micro Columns (50 reactions);
- High Pure RNA Isolation Kit, Roche;
- Affinity Script Multiple Temperature Reverse Transcriptase, Agilent.

Equipment:

- Laminar flow hood;
- Table top centrifuge for 1,5-2ml tubes;
- PCR Thermocycler;
- Heating block – for 1,5ml and 0,2ml tubes;
- Cooled orbital shaker for 96-well plates;
- Nanodrop;
- UV transilluminator and gel documentation system;
- Horizontal Electrophoresis Systems with power supply;

Buffers:

Phosphate buffered saline (PBS) – dissolve one tablet in 200 ml of water for injection (0.1 M phosphate buffer, 0.27 M KCl and 0.137 NaCl), adjust pH to 7.4 at 4 °C; filter through 0.22 µm filter.

Wash buffer (WB): PBS with 50 mM magnesium acetate (MgAc), adjust pH to 7.5 with 1M K₂HPO₄ at 4 °C; filter through 0.22 µm.

Elution buffer (EB): PBS with 250 mM EDTA, adjust pH to 7.5 with acetic acid at 4 °C; filter through 0.22 µm.

Ad 1) Amplification of the SAK gene (library) and PCR gel extraction

- PCR Thermocycler;
- horizontal Electrophoresis Systems with power supply;
- UV transilluminator and gel documentation system;
- heating block – for 1,5 ml and 0,2 ml tubes;
- table top centrifuge for 1,5-2 ml tubes;
- Nanodrop;
- Eppendorf® PCR Cooler or ice;
- RNase free reaction tubes; 1.5 ml and 2 ml micro tubes, 0.2 ml PCR tubes;
- razor blade for cutting gel;
- DNA template (naïve library or SAK gene);
- VentR® DNA Polymerase (2 u/µl; New England Biolabs, No. M0254S) and 10x Thermopol buffer;
- SAK reverse and forward primers (100 µM);
- dNTPs: 5 mM each (NEB, N0447S); aliquot and store at -20 °C;
- RNase, DNase free water;
- agarose standard (e.g. Roth 3810.4) for 1.5% analytical agarose gel in TAE buffer;
- EtBr (5 µl per 75 ml agarose gel);
- 5x or 6x Loading dye and 100 bp DNA Ladder;
- QIAquick Gel Extraction kit (250), Qiagen, Cat. n. 28706.

Ad 2) Restriction digest and ligation of the PCR product into pRDV

- heating block at 37 °C;
- heating block at 70 °C;
- PCR product;
- pRDV;
- restriction enzyme *HindIII* 20 u/µl (e.g. NEB R0104) and *BamHI* 20 u/µl (e.g. NEB R3136S);
- CutSmart buffer;
- nuclease-free water;

- QIAquick PCR purification kit (250);
- T4 DNA ligase and 10x ligase buffer.

Ad 3) PCR on ligation mix and PCR gel extraction

- PCR Thermocycler;
- horizontal Electrophoresis Systems with power supply;
- UV transilluminator and gel documentation system;
- heating block – for 1,5 ml and 0,2 ml tubes;
- table top centrifuge for 1,5-2 ml tubes;
- Nanodrop;
- Eppendorf® PCR Cooler or ice;
- RNase free reaction tubes; 1.5 ml and 2 ml micro tubes, 0.2 ml PCR tubes;
- razor blade for cutting gel;
- primers T7B and tolAkurz dissolved to 100 μ M in H₂O; aliquot and store at –20 °C;
- VentR® DNA Polymerase (2 units/ μ l; New England Biolabs, No. M0254S) and 10x Thermopol buffer;
- Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; Fluka, 41640);
- dNTPs: 5 mM each (NEB, N0447S); aliquot and store at -20 °C;
- nuclease-free water;
- analytical agarose gel (i.e. 1% in TAE buffer);
- EtBr (5 μ l per 75 ml agarose gel);
- 100 bp DNA Ladder;
- 5x or 6x Loading dye;
- QIAquick Gel Extraction kit (250), Qiagen, Cat. n. 28706.

Ad 5) Plate coating

- cooled orbital shaker for 96-well plates;
- microtite plates;
- adhesive plate seals;
- PBS;
- Human Plasmin;
- 10 % BSA in H₂O;
- nuclease-free water.

Ad 6) In vitro transcription

- heating Block (e.g. Eppendorf Thermomixer);
- RNase free 0.2 ml PCR tubes;
- T7 RNA polymerase;
- 5x T7 RNA polymerase buffer;
- RiboLock Ribonuclease Inhibitor;
- 25 mM Ribonucleotide Solution Mix;
- nuclease-free water;
- Eppendorf® PCR Cooler or ice.

Ad 7) RNA purification

- Illustra ProbeQuant™ G-50 Micro Columns and LN2;
- table top Centrifuge;
- Nanodrop device.

Ad 8) In vitro translation

- heating block (37 °C);
- laminar flow hood;
- box with ice and LN2;
- mRNA as template *for in vitro* translation;
- S30 extract;
- PremixZ;
- Heparin;
- Methionine;
- WB buffer;
- STOP solution.

Ad 9) Selection in plates

- cooled orbital shaker for 96-well plates;
- microtitre plate with adhered plasmin;
- adhesive plate seals (Thermo Scientific / Milian, AB-0580);
- WB and PBS;
- elution buffer EB (add 50 µg/ml *S. cerevisiae* RNA before use);

- paper towel;
- *S. cerevisiae* RNA: *S. cerevisiae* RNA: dissolve slowly to 25 µg/µl in H₂O; aliquot and store at -20 °C.

Ad 12) RNA purification

- cooled table top centrifuge;
- 1.5 ml RNase-free tubes;
- filter tips;
- Roche high pure RNA isolation kit;
- box of ice and liquid nitrogen.

Ad 13) Reverse transcription (RT)

- heating block at 70 °C and 50 °C;
- laminar flow hood;
- Eppendorf® PCR Cooler or ice;
- eluted mRNA from panning;
- primer SAK Rev;
- dNTPs: 5 mM each; aliquot and store at -20 °C;
- RiboLock RNase inhibitor;
- AffinityScript™ Multiple Temperature Reverse Transcriptase and 10x buffer;
- 100 mM DTT in H₂O; aliquot and store at -20°C;
- nuclease-free water;
- liquid Nitrogen

Ad 14) PCR on RT

- PCR Thermocycler;
- UV transilluminator and gel documentation system;
- horizontal Electrophoresis Systems with power supply;
- Eppendorf® PCR Cooler or ice;
- primers SAK Fw and Rev (HPLC grade) dissolved to 100 µM in H₂O; aliquot and store at -20 °C;
- cDNA template from RT;
- VentR® DNA Polymerase (2 units/µl; New England Biolabs, No. M0254S) and 10x Thermopol buffer;
- dNTPs: 5 mM each aliquot and store at -20 °C;
- nuclease-free water;

- analytical agarose gel (i.e. 1.5 % (w/v)) in TAE buffer;
- EtBr (10 mg/ml);
- DNA size marker;
- 6x gel loading dye.

Protocol:**DAY 1**

Amplification of the SAK gene (library)

- at least 8 reactions needed to obtain enough amount of DNA

PCR master mix	1x (µl)
Water	20
10X Thermopol buffer	2,5
SAK_FW	0,25
SAK_Rev	0,25
dNTPs	0,5
Vent DNA polymerase	0,5
Total - without DNA	24
DNA	1
Total	25

Digestion (at least 3 µg of DNA):

H₂O + DNA + CutSmart
 + BamHI (20 U/1 µl DNA)
 + HindIII (20 U/1 µl DNA) 1 hod, 37 °C
 HindIII inactivation 20 min, 80 °C

No gel, purification of restriction product by **Qiagen PCR purification kit**

Ligation final volume 20 µl

- 3-4 reactions needed to obtain enough amount of DNA for RD

Gene	c. (ng/ul) digested gene	c. (ng/ul) digested plasmid	Gene volume (ul)	Plasmid volume (ul)	Volume T4 DNA ligase (ul) 5u/ul	Volume T4B (ul)	Volume H ₂ O (ul)	Total volume
SAK digest								

Pre-incubation: 10 min, 65 °C, 0 rpm - plasmid, gene, water
Ligation: 1 hour, 20 min, 0 rpm
Heat inactivation: 5 min, 70 °C

DAY 2

PCR on ligation mix

- 6-8 reactions needed to obtain enough amount of DNA

PCR (50 ul)	1x (µl)
<i>T7B (100 µM)</i>	0,5
<i>ToIAkurz (100 µM)</i>	0,5
<i>DMSO</i>	3
<i>dNTPs (10 mM)</i>	1
<i>10x Thermopol buffer</i>	5
<i>Vent DNA polymerase (2 U/µl)</i>	1
<i>Water</i>	29
<i>Total - without DNA</i>	40
<i>Ligation mix</i>	10
Total	50

Cycling: 1x (3 min 95 °C); 35x (30 s 95 °C, 30 s 55 °C, 70 s 72 °C); 1x 5 min 72 °C;

Gel: 1 %; PCR purification by **Qiagen Gel extraction kit**; DNA quality check;

Product length: 873 bp;

We need at least **1,5 µg** of DNA for *IV* Transcription.

Plate coating:

Ligand: pipette 2 x 100 µl plasmin/well;

Negative control (NC): pipette 100 µl of 0.5 % BSA/well;

Incubate: 4 °C, O/N, 300 rpm.

Preparation:

Prepare following tubes:

IV transcription 0.2 ml: 1;

mRNA 1.5 ml: 1;

mRNA diluted *1.5 ml*: 1;

IV translation *1.5 ml*: 1;

STOP solution *1.5 ml*: 1;

Stopped IV translation *1.5 ml*: 1;

EB+cs RNA *1.5 ml*: 1;

mRNA purification lysis *1.5 ml*: 3;

mRNA purification elution *1.5cml*: 3;

PCR, RT+/- master mix *1.5 ml*: 3;

RT+ *0,2 ml*: 3;

RT- *0.2 ml*: 3;

PCR *0.2 ml*: 6.

UV for 20 minutes: pipettes, prepared tubes, H₂O and filtered tips.

DAY 3 (~ 10 hours)

IV Transcription (ivTr)

- Amount of PCR product and water depend on the DNA concentration from step 4; at least 1,5 µg of DNA.
- DNase from High Pure RNA Isolation Kit, Roche, Cat. n. 11828665001, Stock: 182 U/ µl (910 U DNase/50 µl reaction).

Transcription: 37°C, 2.5 h, 0rpm (0,2ml strip)
DNase treatment – RT, 10min, 5µl DNase/50µl reaction; right after ivTr
mRNA purification - kit Illustra ProbeQuant G-50 Micro columns

ivTranscription	1x (µl)
<i>5x T7 buffer</i>	10
<i>10x Thermopol buffer</i>	3
<i>NTP mix (25 mM)</i>	14
<i>T7 RNA polymerase (20 U/µl)</i>	2,5
<i>RiboLock (40 U/µl)</i>	1
<i>Water</i>	9,5
<i>Total - without DNA</i>	40
<i>PCR product (1,5-2 µg)</i>	10
Total	50

mRNA purification protocol:

- vortex column to resuspend the inner matrix;
- break the bottom of the column;
- spin down the column for 1 min at 750 g;
- place the column in to a new 1.5 ml collection tube (**mRNA not-diluted**);
- apply sample at the top of the column (~ 50 µl);
- spin down for 1 min at 750 g;
- recover the sample at the collection tube - **mRNA not-diluted**;
- **dilute mRNA 20x** - 5µl mRNA + 95 µl H₂O for measurement of concentration on Nanodrop;
- immediately flash freeze the rest of mRNA in LN₂.

IV Translation

- Amount of RNA and water depend on RNA concentration; at least 10 µg of RNA.

ivTranslation	1x (µl)
<i>Met 200 mM</i>	2
<i>PremixZ</i>	41
<i>S30 extract</i>	50
<i>H₂O</i>	
RNA (10 µg z ivTc)	
Total	110

Translation: 37 °C, 7 min (1,5 ml micro tubes).

Prepare 440 µl/translation stop solution:

Stop solution	1x (µl)	1
<i>WBT</i>	412,5	412,5
<i>10 % BSA</i>	22	22
<i>200 mg/ml Heparin</i>	5,5	5,5
Total	440	440

- Pipette 100 µl of translation reaction into the 440 µl pre-cooled stopping buffer;
- centrifuge:** 20 000 g for 5 min at 4°C;
- put tubes into the ice until they are used.

Ribosome display in plates

- Pipette 100 µl/well of stopped solution in to the wells (with ligand and NC);
- cover wells with the plastic seal and incubate at **4 °C, 300 rpm, 60 min.**

Washing: in the 1st round **1x** 400 µl WB/well; 2nd round **2-3x** 400 µl WB/well; 3rd round **5-6x** 400 µl WB/well.

Elution buffer	1x (µl)
<i>Elution buffer</i>	200
<i>RNA <i>S. cerevisiae</i> (25 µg/ml)</i>	0,4
Total	200,4

Elution

- Add 200 µl/well of cold elution buffer (EB) with *S. cerevisiae* mRNA and shake for **4 °C, 900 rpm, 10 min.**
- Pipette the eluate (200 µl) directly into previously prepared 400 µl COLD LYSIS buffer of Roche RNA purification kit and vortex for 15 seconds.
- **Set** two heating blocks: 50 °C (0.2 ml, RT) and 70 °C (1.5 ml tubes, mRNA denaturation).

Eluted mRNA purification (all centrifugation steps are done at 4 °C)

- Apply the **lysis buffer mixture** (600 µl) eluted from RD on the column.
- Spin for 1 min at 8000 g, discard flow through.
- Add **500 µl Wash Buffer I (black cap)**, centrifuge for **1 minute at 8 000 g**, discard flow through.
- Add **500 µl Wash Buffer II (blue cap)**, centrifuge for **1 minute at 8 000 g**, discard flow through.
- Add **100 µl Wash Buffer II (blue cap)** and spin for **2 min at 13 000 g**.
- Elute with **50 µl Elution buffer (transparent cap)** and spin for **1 min at 8 000 g**.
- Denature RNA at **70 °C for 10 min.**

Reverse transcription

- During the 10 minutes of denaturation, pipette reverse transcription reaction in laminar flow hood.

Reverse transcription	1x (µl)
	RT
<i>Water</i>	2
<i>10x RT buffer</i>	2
<i>DTT</i>	2
<i>Primer rev SAK</i>	0,25
<i>dNTPs</i>	0,5
<i>RiboLock</i>	0,5
<i>Affinity Script RT</i>	0,5
<i>Total – without RNA</i>	7,75
<i>Eluted mRNA (denaturated)</i>	12,25
Total	20

Reverse transcription: 50 °C, 50 min, 0 rpm (0,2 ml micro tubes)

- Use – 2-5 µl for PCR, freeze the rest in LN2; in 1st round use 1-2 µl, in the following rounds use 5 µl.

PCR with cDNA

6. PCR	1x (µl)
<i>Water</i>	16,775
<i>10x Thermopol buffer</i>	2,5
<i>SAK_FW</i>	0,05
<i>SAK_Rev</i>	0,05
<i>dNTPs</i>	0,5
<i>Vent DNA polymerase</i>	0,125
<i>Total - bez DNA</i>	20
<i>cDNA (1 to 5 µl)</i>	5
Total	25

Cycling: 1x (3 min 95 °C); 10x (30 s 95 °C, 45 s 70-61 °C, 50 s 72 °C); 15-30x (30 s 95 °C, 45 s 60 °C, 50 s 72 °C); 1x 5 min 72 °C.

Gel: 1.5 %; PCR purification by **Qiagen Gel extraction kit**; DNA quality check.

Figure 2. Controls and quality assessment of selection.

Figure 3. Results from RD SAK.

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4. Students' presentations

Presentation of a group A

CasProt
Summer school

DIRECTED EVOLUTION OF PROTEINS

2nd – 12th May 2023, Košice

Group A

Workflow and results

Ribosome display (RD)

- Cell-free method
- *In vitro* protein evolution
- Protein binding to desired ligand
- Result is a genotype associated with phenotype
- Isolation of excellent binders and decription of binder sequence only when necessary

Comparison of RD with other selection methods

- Cell- based and cell-free methods

LIMITATIONS

- cell-based methods:
 - low efficiency of transformation- smallest and less diverse libraries
 - in vitro to invivo
 - laborious and time-consuming
- cell-free methods:
 - low stability of ternary complexes
 - nucleases, proteases, and other inhibitory factors inevitably appear in the cell-extract-based cell-free translation systems

RD steps

- Error-prone PCR
- Ligation
- Amplification (T7 RBS, toIA)
- In vitro* transcription
- In vitro* translation
- Selection
- Purification and reverse transcription
- Amplification

Highlights about RD to remember

- No stop codon
- Need RBS and linker (toIA)
- In RD always work on ice, sterile, RNase free
- S30 extract for translation
- Prepanning with BSA
- Buffer used for RD: PBS, pH 7.4
- Washing buffer with high magnesium content
- Elution buffer with EDTA and *S. cerevisiae* RNA

Where can we use RD in our lab?

- Michael Mareš Group
- Group of molecular biology and biochemistry
- Cathepsin proteases in pathology
- Screening of AA mutations of protein inhibitor loops and their impact on binding mode to target protease

Our workflow

- Steps:
 - I. Error-prone PCR
 - II. Ligation to pQE plasmid
 - III. Amplification (T7 RBS, tolA)
 - IV. *In vitro* transcription
 - V. *In vitro* translation
 - VI. Selection
 - VII. Purification and reverse transcription
 - VIII. Amplification

Error-prone PCR

- Amplification of SAK gene (10 μ M)
- **8-oxo-dGTP** and **dPTP analogues**
- Taq-polymerase without proofreading activity
- Touchdown PCR
- 1.5% agarose gel
- Extraction of mutated DNA

Visualization of error-prone PCR products.

Ligation to pQE plasmid

- Digestion of DNA after error-prone PCR
- 3 μg of DNA digested

ng/ μL	A_{260}/A_{280}	A_{260}/A_{230}
132.7	1.88	0.65

- Restriction enzymes: **BamHI** and **HindIII**
- 130 ng of insert DNA
- T4 DNA Ligase
- **pQE plasmid** (for sequencing)
- Transformation (chemical) to E.coli XL1 Blue

Amplification (T7 RBS, toIA)

- **pRDV**
- Adding T7 RBS and toIA into insert
- Vent DNA polymerase
- Ligation mixture containing pRDV and insert

Amplified PCR products after ligation of insert with RBS and toIA.

Preparing of wells and *In vitro* transcription

- pre-coated wells/plate with electrophilic linkers
- L - plasmin, BSA and NC – 1%BSA, O/N, 4°C, 150rpm

- PCR product (1.6 µg) - SAK Frida Library outer
- T7 RNA polymerase
- RiboLock
- 37°C, 3hrs
- DNase treatment
- mRNA purification

In vitro translation

- purified mRNA: 800 ng/µL (13.6 µg)
- **S30 extract (ribosomes)**, PremixZ + Met
- 37°C, 7min

- Stop reaction (BSA + heparin)
- release of ternary complex
- 4°C, 5min, 20 000 x g

Selection and purification

- prepanning, 30min, non-specific bindings
- supernatant into panning wells (L+NC)

- elution
- RNA *S.cerevisiae*

- purification
- DNase treatment

Reverse transcription and PCR

- Denatured mRNA, 70°C, 10min
- *Primer rev SAK Frida*, RiboLock, Affinity Script RT
- 50°C, 50min
- Touchdown PCR:
3 samples (NC+RT, NC-RT, I+, I-, L+, L-, H₂O)

Conclusion

- Created SAK library
- Transformation to pRDV
- Transcription, translation steps
- Pros: confirmation of non-contamination of solutions

Presentation of a group B

CasProt

Summer School on Directed Evolution of Proteins

2nd – 12th May 2023, Košice

PARTNERS
AND
ORGANIZERS

Directed evolution of proteins

- Main goal: To obtain antibodies/proteins with high affinity and high stability against the target of interest

The flowchart illustrates the process of directed evolution of proteins, organized into three horizontal rows: DNA Variants, Display, and Screening.

1. **DNA Variants**: This row includes 'Computational Design' (with sub-methods 'Site-mutagenesis' and 'Metagenome') and 'Random Mutagenesis' (with sub-methods 'Eq-PCR', 'DNA shuffling', and 'SEEP').

2. **Display**: This row includes 'In Vivo display' (with sub-methods 'E. coli library', 'Phage display', and 'Virus-like capsule') and 'In Vitro display' (with sub-methods 'RNA or DNA display', 'Ribosome display', and 'Liposome display').

3. **Screening**: This row includes 'Screening' (with sub-methods 'Agar plate', 'Biopanning', and 'IAN-PCR') and 'Screening' (with sub-methods 'SIMPLEX', 'FACS', and 'CFCA').

Arrows indicate the flow from DNA Variants to Display, and from Display to Screening.

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Selection systems

Library size: $10^{10} - 10^{12}$ $10^6 - 10^8$ $10^2 - 10^3$

The diagram shows three selection systems:

1. **Ribosome display**: Represented by a ribosome with a protein chain attached. Library size: $10^{10} - 10^{12}$.

2. **Phage display**: Represented by a phage particle with a protein on its tail. Library size: $10^6 - 10^8$.

3. **Cell-surface display**: Represented by a cell with a protein on its surface. Library size: $10^2 - 10^3$.

- Advantages of ribosome display:
 - In vitro cell-free (no limits of transformation efficiency)
 - Large diversity of libraries ($10^{13} \sim 10^{14}$)
 - Easy random mutations generation every round

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Ribosome display

- *in vitro* cell-free selection and directed evolution technology for proteins and peptides from large libraries

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Mutations

- ↑ Error-rate of PC
 - Non-proof-reading enzyme (Taq polymerase) / error-prone mutated polymerase
 - Nucleotide analogues (dPTP, oxo-dGTP)
 - Conditions (↑ PCR cycles)

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Library layout

- Stop codon – removed

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Selection

- Strength of binding with a target molecule immobilized on a plate or micro-beads

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Staphylokinase (SAK)

- Plasminogen activator staphylokinase
→ fibrin-specific thrombolytic biomolecule

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Goal

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Wild-type staphylokinase

Engineered staphylokinase

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1st part

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- Error-prone PCR = amplification of the SAK gene
- 2 different concentrations of nucleotide analogues (3 μ M and 10 μ M) 8-oxo-dGTP and dPTP

1st part

- Analyze PCR product on 1,5% agarose gel
- Purify DNA from the gel using gel extraction kit
- Measure the concentration of DNA - using NanoDrop

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Visualization of error-prone PCR products – SAK DNA library

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1st part

- Restriction Digestion with enzymes
HindIII, BamHI
- Purification
- Ligation
- pRDV – for ribosome display
- pQE – sequencing

Transformation(chemical) – to E.coli XL1 Blue and E.coli DH5α =

50ul and 100ul of transformed cell suspension onto 2YT agar plates

Plasmid isolation (XL1 Blue) – for sequencing

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1st part

- PCR on ligation mix (pRDV)
- Analyze PCR product on 1,5% agarose gel
- Extract DNA from the gel using a gel extraction kit
- Purification

RIBOSOME DISPLAY

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Amplified PCR products after ligation

2nd part

Selection

1. Wash (MgAc)
2. Elution (EDTA)

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2nd part

1. Purification
2. Denaturation
3. Reverse transcription

cDNA

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2nd part

Reverse transcription

L+RT L-RT NC+RT NC-RT I+RT I-RT

PCR

L+RT L-RT NC+RT NC-RT I+RT I-RT water

asProt

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Closing remarks

- RNases are everywhere
- Labeling is a must
- Prepare everything
- Avoid DNA contamination
- **Cry is allowed**, but clean the space from RNases when you are done

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